

IPBES transformative change assessment Chapter 5. Data Management Report 5.2 Literature review on harmful subsidies

Versioning 01: 11/2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13789299>

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The scoping report of the assessment describes that one of the aims for chapter 5 is: “Identifying and providing understanding of factors at various scales in human society [...] that can be leveraged to bring about transformative change”, and what elements impact the patterns of production, supply and consumption on nature, nature’s contributions to people (NCP) and good quality of life. The chapter presents a synthesis and assessment of sets of policies, tools, methods, campaigns, frameworks, finance instruments, options and actions enabling and encouraging transformative change at all scales for a sustainable world. Section 5.4.3 includes an assessment of the global volume of public subsidies to sectors that drive biodiversity loss and nature decline, and then whether subsidies are presented as “positive”, “neutral”, or “negative” in the literature.

This Data Management Report is supplemented by technical reports on the transformative change assessment corpus of literature available here: https://ipbes-data.github.io/IPBES_TCA_Corpus/

Process overview

Protocol

Type of analysis/search/review: Literature search performed in the transformative change assessment corpus of literature.

Search languages: English

Search engine: Scopus

Exact date of the search: 22 November 2023

Search terms:

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Biodiversity") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("harmful incentive" OR "harmful subsidy") AND [EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "MEDI") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA, "NURS")]

Sample extracted: 11 records

Fields extracted:

- Authors
- Author full names
- Author(s) ID
- Title
- Year
- Source title
- Volume
- Issue
- Art. No.
- Page start
- Page end
- Page count
- Cited by
- DOI
- Link
- Abstract
- Author Keywords
- Index Keywords
- Abbreviated Source Title
- Document Type
- Publication Stage
- Open Access
- Source
- EID
- Remarks

Location and format of the data (A): 1_IPBES_TCA_DMR 5.2_references subsidies_11_2024_(A).bib

Treatment applied: Documents referring to government support to different economic sectors that directly drive nature decline (n=124,517 hits) were selected from the transformative

change assessment corpus of literature. A sentiment analysis of words of the document's abstract was performed to understand whether subsidies are presented as "positive", "neutral", or "negative" in the literature. A temporal analysis to identify trends between 1900 and 2020 was also conducted and presented in the figure SM5.8 (in supplementary materials of chapter 5).

Document providing global data on the number of subsidies provided were selected, choosing:

- Documents that reflected most updated information
- Documents with a global coverage

Additional empirical and conceptual articles not covered by the literature search but known by the authors to be relevant for the topic and snowball sampling from documents originally identified have been included as well to obtain the final list. The sector related to the subsidies, its outcome and the financial value of the subsidies were identified to carry out statistical descriptive analyses throughout section 5.4.3. and for the figure SM.5.9 / figure SPM7.

Definitions of files

ID	Names	File Type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_DMR 5.2_references subsidies_11_2024_(A). bib	Bib Tex	15 KB	Eleven documents on subsidies of sectors driving nature's decline